

Carbon Footprint Considerations with Optical Transceiver Evolution

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10th International Symposium
on Optical Interconnect in Data Centers
-Session 1-
Tuesday, 24th September 2024

AWS, Google, Verizon, Microsoft: ~90 % of Datacenters worldwide

Source: OMDIA2023

~30% of Ireland National energy consumption in 2028

London #1

42%

24%

21%

AWS, Google, Verizon, Microsoft: ~90 % of Datacenters worldwide

2025 and beyond: An industry that keeps improving and optimizing

Data center electricity consumption and share of global electricity consumption, 2010–50

Source: OMDIA2023

IT and infrastructure design optimized for energy efficiency
 Server virtualization ramps, reaches saturation
 Highly distributed server architecture (high volume, low cost, low power servers)

Investment in AI pushes up DC power consumption

AI computing gets optimized
 Nuclear microgrids ramp
 AI-powered, centralized DC energy management, backup, and microgrid control

New wave of DC IT optimization
 Quantum computing ramps up for scientific problem solving/HPC

Source: Omdia

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Orange Data Centers in France ~6% global Orange France power consumption (GWh) (2023)

Our objectives in 2030

Close 17 legacy Data Centers

some functions moved in existing Central Offices
(edge servers & computing)

Keep only 3 new generation DCs

Val-de-Reuil 1 (2012)
Val-de-Reuil 2 (2022)
Amily (2022)

~10.5/12 months in free cooling
reduce by 30 % energy footprint

100% renewable energy with PPA

PUE : 1.3 WUE ~ 0 CUE 0,087

Objective: Net Zero Carbon in 2040

PPA: Purchase Plan Agreement ; PUE, WUE, CUE: Power, Water, Carbon Usage Effectiveness

Orange & Carbon footprint Our commitment: reduce our CO₂ emissions in Scope 1, 2 and 3

French Digital Sector (CO₂)

Source: ADEME-ARCEP report 2022

Orange France (CO₂)

Data Center interconnects: a digital sustainability question

Growing demand for digital services and high-speed connectivity

Data center carbon footprint optimisation

Energy mix is linked to carbon intensity of electricity generation (g CO₂e/kWh)

Carbon intensity of electricity generation, 2023

Carbon intensity is measured in grams of carbon dioxide-equivalents¹ emitted per kilowatt-hour² of electricity generated.

Data source: Ember (2024); Energy Institute - Statistical Review of World Energy (2024)

OurWorldInData.org/en

Data center carbon footprint optimisation

Capacity to produce enough energy volume is also important to optimize Data Center location

Data center carbon footprint optimisation

Low carbon transportation

Electric/Hybrid Vehicles

Optimized shipment, routes & plannings

Local sourcing

Increase Equipment Life Span

Smart upgrades, consolidation

All-photonic TOR switch

Refurbish

Repair

Repurpose

Recycle

Optimize usage

Virtualization, cloud

Decrease equipment power consumption

Transmission equipment

Servers, Optimise CPU usage,

Minimize cooling needs

Optimize Data Center location (free cooling)

Immersion cooling (high PUE, new servers/rooms)

- up to 80% savings

Towards 100% renewable energy

solar, wind, hydroelectric, geothermal or PPA

Example of DC CO₂e distribution

Varies according to

Datacenter location

Equipment energy efficiency (PUE)

Energy mix

Other carbon footprint reduction?

For Orange France, **Networks represent 50-60%** of the GHG footprint

👁️ **Optical Access networks?**

Deployment of future PON technologies while reducing our CO2 impact

- Increase split ratio from 1:64 → 1:128 → 256?

Top Scored - W4D1 - 4.00 p.m

Field trial of the first G-PON, XGS-PON, 50G-PON triple-MPM reaching >35 dB ODN OPL with 20 km reach

Fabienne Saliou⁽¹⁾, Gaël Simon⁽¹⁾, Joseph Zandueti⁽¹⁾, Aude Rodriguez⁽¹⁾, Stéphane Le Huérou⁽¹⁾, Philippe Chanclou⁽¹⁾, Jérémy Potet⁽¹⁾, Guillaume Vu-Brugier⁽²⁾

Oral paper - W4D2 - 4.30 p.m

High Power Integrated DFB-EAM-SOA for beyond 35 dB Optical Path Loss 50G-PON and Raman Scattering Estimations

Gaël Simon⁽¹⁾, Jérémy Potet⁽¹⁾, Dylan Chevalier⁽¹⁾, Fabienne Saliou⁽¹⁾, Philippe Chanclou⁽¹⁾, Takumi Fujigaki⁽²⁾, Daiki Tanabe⁽²⁾, Toru Hirayama⁽²⁾, Yoshinori Kannan⁽²⁾, Luiz Anet Neto⁽³⁾

- Implement and impose use of sleep modes in Networks equipment & Residential Gateways

Poster P2A.124
Wednesday 11.00 a,m

Power Consumption and CO₂ Emission Optimization for Future Passive Optical Networks

Aude Rodriguez⁽¹⁾, Fabienne Saliou⁽¹⁾, Stéphane Le Huérou⁽¹⁾, Pòmmè Broggi⁽¹⁾, Michał Szymański⁽¹⁾, Gaël Simon⁽¹⁾, Jérémy Potet⁽¹⁾, Philippe Chanclou⁽¹⁾

- Using COMBO Multi-PON Modules integrating G-PON, XGS-PON and 50G-PON optics in a single transceiver

→Energy and space saving

Multiple optics integration in DATACOM transceivers?

Multi-rate options?

“auto-neg” like >10Gbit/s?

enabling low-rate sleep modes?

Other carbon footprint reductions?

Optimize Next Generation Central Offices

Critical nodes for

Traffic, service, customer aggregation,
Network management, orchestration, monitoring and maintenance
Content delivery, data collection, edge computing (Mobile & AI)

Future evolution with

Increased switching capacity
Increased flexibility
Increased transparency
Increased security
TSN features (low latency & jitter)

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OCTAPUS
EU project

 YouTube

In this symposium
Session 4, this afternoon 3.30 p.m :

OCTAPUS Project – Optical Circuit switched Time sensitive network architecture for high-speed Passive optical networks and next generation Ultra-dynamic & reconfigurable central office environments
Chris Vagionas (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki)

Thank you ! Merci !

Fabienne Saliou

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